

THE DIOPHANTINE EQUATION $\sum_{j=1}^k j f_j^p = l_n^q$

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Abstract

In this paper, we consider the Diophantine equation $F_1^p + 2F_2^p + \cdots + kF_k^p = L_n^q$ in positive integer variables (k, n, p, q) , where F_i is the i^{th} term of the Fibonacci sequence and L_i the i^{th} term of its companion Lucas sequence. We prove that this equation has only finitely many nontrivial solutions.

1. Introduction

Let $(F_n)_{n \geq 0}$ be the Fibonacci sequence given by

$$F_0 = 0, F_1 = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad F_n = F_{n-1} + F_{n-2}, \quad \text{for } n \geq 2.$$

The initial terms of this sequence are

$$0, 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, 34, 55, 89, 144, \dots$$

The Lucas sequence $(L_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is given by

$$L_0 = 2, L_1 = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad L_n = L_{n-1} + L_{n-2}, \quad \text{for } n \geq 2.$$

The initial terms of this sequence are

$$2, 1, 3, 4, 7, 11, 18, 29, 47, 76, 123, 199, 322, 521, 843, \dots$$

Let $(\alpha, \beta) = ((1 + \sqrt{5})/2, (1 - \sqrt{5})/2)$ be the roots of the characteristic equation $x^2 - x - 1 = 0$ of the Fibonacci sequence. Binet's formula for F_n is

$$F_n = \frac{\alpha^n - \beta^n}{\sqrt{5}}, \quad \text{for } n \geq 0. \tag{1.1}$$

This easily implies that

$$\alpha^{n-2} \leq F_n \leq \alpha^{n-1}, \quad \text{for } n \geq 1. \tag{1.2}$$

It is easy to prove that

$$\frac{F_n}{F_{n+1}} \leq \frac{2}{3}, \quad \text{for } n \geq 2. \tag{1.3}$$

It is also easy to check that

$$F_1 + F_2 + \dots + F_n = F_{n+2} - 1, \quad \text{for } n \geq 0. \tag{1.4}$$

Binet's formula for L_n is

$$L_n = \alpha^n + \beta^n, \quad \text{for } n \geq 0. \tag{1.5}$$

Similarly, this implies the inequalities

$$\alpha^{n-1} \leq L_n \leq \alpha^{n+1}, \quad \text{for } n \geq 2. \tag{1.6}$$

Observe that

$$\begin{aligned} F_1 &= L_1, & F_1^2 &= L_1. \\ F_1 + 2F_2 &= L_2, & F_1^2 + 2F_2^2 &= L_2 \\ F_1 + 2F_2 + 3F_3 &= L_2^2. \end{aligned} \tag{1.7}$$

The natural question that arises is the following:

is $F_1^p + 2F_2^p + \dots + kF_k^p$ a power of a Lucas number?

The aim of this paper is to give an answer to this question.

For a quick history, the Diophantine equation

$$\sum_{j=1}^k jF_j^p = F_n^q$$

has been studied in 2018 by G. Soydan, L. Németh, and L. Szalay [8], where F_i is the i^{th} Fibonacci number. They solved this equation for $(p, q) \in \{(1, 1), (1, 2), (2, 1), (2, 2)\}$. Further, they conjectured that the only non-trivial solutions are given by:

$$F_4^2 = 9 = F_1 + 2F_2 + 3F_3, \quad F_8 = 21 = F_1 + 2F_2 + 3F_3 + 4F_4, \quad F_4^3 = 27 = F_1^3 + 2F_2^3 + 3F_3^3.$$

In 2019, K. Gueth, F. Luca and L. Szalay [3] confirmed the conjecture, for $\max\{p, q\} \leq 10$. This result was again improved by Altassan and Luca [1] who proved that if such an equation is satisfied, then $\max\{k, n, p, q\} \leq 10^{2500}$. The second and third authors of this paper studied a similar equation, where the Fibonacci sequence is replaced by the Pell sequence (see [9]).

In this paper, we investigate the Diophantine equation

$$F_1^p + 2F_2^p + \dots + kF_k^p = L_n^q. \tag{1.8}$$

We consider the solution given by

$$F_1^p = 1 = L_1^q,$$

as well as the solutions given by

$$F_1^p + 2F_2^p = 3 = L_2,$$

as trivial solution to (1.8). We will ignore such solutions. So, we consider $k \geq 3$, which implies that $n \geq 2$.

Note that even the case $p = 0$ leads to some interesting equations. Indeed, $p = 0$ gives

$$\sum_{j=1}^k j = L_n^q,$$

i.e.,

$$\frac{k(k+1)}{2} = \binom{k+1}{2} = L_n^q.$$

All perfect powers in binomial coefficients have been found by Györy [4]. His result implies that $q \leq 2$ i.e., $q = 1$ or $q = 2$.

For $q = 1$, we get a Lucas number which is a triangular number ($L_n = k(k+1)/2$) and the only such are $L_1 = 1$, $L_2 = 3$, and $L_{18} = 5778$ (see [6]). The corresponding values of k are respectively $k = 1$, $k = 2$, and $k = 107$. So the only solutions of our equation (1.8) in this case are $(k, n, p, q) \in \{(1, 1, 0, 1), (2, 3, 0, 1), (107, 18, 0, 1)\}$.

For $q = 2$, we get $(2k+1)^2 - 2(2L_n)^2 = 1$. So, $L_n = P_{2m}/2$ is the half of an even Pell number (or a balancing number) and it is known that there is no balancing number which is a term of the Lucas sequence. This is a result due to K. Liptai in 2006 [5].

In this paper, we consider the case of positive variables and prove the following result.

Theorem 1. *The Diophantine Equation (1.8) has only finitely many solutions in positive integers variables k, n, p, q , with $k \geq 3$. Such solutions satisfy $\max\{k, n, p, q\} < 10^{2100}$.*

Our proof uses techniques from Diophantine approximations such as lower bounds for linear forms in logarithms of algebraic numbers that we will recall later.

2. Proof of Theorem 1

Recall that we are studying the Diophantine equation

$$\sum_{j=1}^k jF_j^p = L_n^q.$$

Put

$$s := \sum_{j=1}^k jF_j^p = L_n^q \quad \text{and} \quad x := \log s. \tag{2.1}$$

Our purpose is to bound x . Observe that

$$(\alpha^{k/3})^p \leq (\alpha^{k-2})^p < F_k^p < s$$

and

$$s < k \left(\sum_{j=1}^k F_j \right)^p < k(F_{k+2})^p < k\alpha^{(k+1)p} < \alpha^{(k+1)p+3 \log k} < \alpha^{3kp},$$

where we used (1.4) to get that $\sum_{j=1}^k F_j < F_{k+2}$. Since $\log \alpha \in (1/3, 1/2)$, one can see that

$$kp/3 < 3 \log s \quad \text{and} \quad 2 \log s < 3kp.$$

We deduce that

$$\frac{2}{3} \log s < kp < 9 \log s,$$

which leads to

$$10^{-1}x < kp < 10x.$$

Similarly, we have

$$(\alpha^{n/2})^q \leq (\alpha^{n-1})^q < s = L_n^q \leq (\alpha^{n+1})^q < \alpha^{2nq}$$

to obtain

$$x < nq < 10x.$$

We record this as a lemma.

Lemma 1. *With the notations given in (2.1), if (k, n, p, q) is a nontrivial solution to (1.8), then*

$$10^{-1}x < kp < 10x \quad \text{and} \quad x < nq < 10x.$$

Next, we will look for positive constants $t_1, t_2,$ and t_3 such that

$$k > x^{t_1}, \quad p > x^{t_2}, \quad \text{and} \quad n > x^{t_3}.$$

Let (k, n, p, q) be a nontrivial solution of the Diophantine Equation (1.8).

2.1. Value of t_1

In this subsection, we will prove the following result.

Lemma 2. *If $x > 10^{150}$, then $k > x^{1/4}$.*

Proof. Assume that $x > 10^{150}$ and that $k \leq x^{1/4}$ in order to get a contradiction. Using the method in [1], we have

$$\begin{aligned} L_n^q = s &= \sum_{j=1}^k jF_j^p = kF_k^p \left(1 + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \binom{k-j}{k} \left(\frac{F_{k-j}}{F_k} \right)^p \right) \\ &= kF_k^p + kF_k^p \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \binom{k-j}{k} \left(\frac{F_{k-j}}{F_k} \right)^p. \end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

Then, one obtains

$$|L_n^q - kF_k^p| = kF_k^p \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \binom{k-j}{k} \left(\frac{F_{k-j}}{F_k} \right)^p$$

and dividing both sides by kF_k^p , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left| (kF_k^p)^{-1} L_n^q - 1 \right| &= \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \binom{k-j}{k} \left(\frac{F_{k-j}}{F_k} \right)^p < 2 \sum_{j \geq 1} \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^{jp} \\ &< \frac{2}{1.5^p} \sum_{j \geq 0} \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^j = \frac{6}{1.5^p}, \end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

where we used (1.3), as well as the fact that $\sum_{j \geq 0} \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^j = 3$.

Before completing the proof of the current lemma, let us recall some necessary results. For any non-zero algebraic number η of degree d over \mathbb{Q} whose minimal polynomial over \mathbb{Z} is $a_0 \prod_{i=1}^d (X - \eta^{(i)})$ with $a_0 > 0$, we denote by

$$h(\eta) = \frac{1}{d} \left(\log a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^d \log \max \{ 1, |\eta^{(i)}| \} \right)$$

the usual absolute logarithmic height of η . We recall Theorem 9.4 of [2], which is a modified version of a result of Matveev [7].

Theorem 2. *Let $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r$ be real algebraic numbers and let b_1, \dots, b_r be nonzero integers. Let D be the degree of the number field $\mathbb{Q}(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_r)$ over \mathbb{Q} and let A_j be a positive real number satisfying*

$$A_j \geq \max\{Dh(\alpha_j), |\log \alpha_j|, 0.16\} \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, r.$$

Assume that

$$B \geq \max\{|b_1|, \dots, |b_r|\}.$$

If $\Lambda = \prod_{j=1}^r \alpha_j^{b_j} - 1 \neq 0$, then

$$\left| \prod_{j=1}^r \alpha_j^{b_j} - 1 \right| \geq \exp(-1.4 \cdot 30^{r+3} \cdot r^{4.5} \cdot D^2(1 + \log D)(1 + \log B)A_1 \cdots A_r).$$

Put

$$\Lambda_1 := (kF_k^p)^{-1} L_n^q - 1.$$

We check that $\Lambda_1 \neq 0$. Indeed, from equation (1.8), we have

$$0 < \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} jF_j^p = -(kF_k^p - L_n^q),$$

which implies that

$$\Lambda_1 > 0.$$

We will use Matveev's theorem to get a lower bound for Λ_1 . Put

$$r := 3, \alpha_1 := k, \alpha_2 := F_k, \alpha_3 := L_n, \quad b_1 := -1, \quad b_2 := -p, \quad b_3 := q.$$

Note that $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3 \in \mathbb{Q}$. Thus, we take $D := 1$. Since

$$h(\alpha_1) = \log k < \log(10x), \quad h(\alpha_2) = \log F_k < 0.5k, \quad \text{and } h(\alpha_3) = \log L_n < n,$$

we take $A_1 := \log(10x)$, $A_2 := 0.5k$, $A_3 := n$. Finally, by Lemma 1, $B := 10x > \max |b_i|$. Hence, Matveev's theorem implies that

$$\log |\Lambda_1| \geq -1.4 \times 30^6 \times 3^{4.5} \times 1^2 \times (1 + \log 1)(1 + \log(10x))(\log(10x))(0.5k)(n).$$

So, we obtain

$$\log |\Lambda_1| > -1.44 \times 10^{10} kn (\log(10x))^2, \tag{2.4}$$

where we used the fact that $1 + \log(10x) < 2 \log(10x)$. Thus, Inequalities (2.3) and (2.4) imply that

$$p < 3.56 \times 10^{11} kn (\log(10x))^2.$$

By Lemma 1, we observe that $n < 10x/q < 100kp/q$. So, we have $p < 3.56 \times 10^{11} k(100kp/q) (\log(10x))^2$, which leads to

$$q < 3.56 \times 10^{13} k^2 (\log(10x))^2. \tag{2.5}$$

Since $k \leq x^{1/4}$, we get that $q < 3.56 \times 10^{13} x^{1/2} (\log(10x))^2$. Thus, we obtain

$$n > x/q > 2.8 \times 10^{-14} x^{1/2} / (\log(10x))^2 > x^{1/3},$$

as $x > 10^{150}$. Hence, we have $q < 10x/n < 10x^{2/3} < 10n^2 < n^3$. The inequalities $n > x^{1/3} > 10^{50}$ lead to

$$\frac{q}{\alpha^{2n}} < \frac{n^3}{\alpha^{2n}} < \frac{1}{\alpha^n},$$

where we used the fact that $n^3 < \alpha^n$ for $n \geq 19$.

On the other hand, we have

$$L_n^q = (\alpha^n + \beta^n)^q = \alpha^{nq} \left(1 + \frac{(-1)^n}{\alpha^{2n}} \right)^q.$$

If n is odd, then

$$\begin{aligned} 1 > \left(1 + \frac{(-1)^n}{\alpha^{2j}} \right)^q &= \left(1 - \frac{1}{\alpha^{2n}} \right)^q = \exp \left(q \log \left(1 - \frac{1}{\alpha^{2n}} \right) \right) \\ &> \exp \left(-\frac{q}{\alpha^{2n}} \right) > \exp \left(-\frac{1}{\alpha^n} \right) \\ &> 1 - \frac{2}{\alpha^n} \end{aligned}$$

because $\frac{1}{\alpha^n} < \alpha^{-10^{150}}$ is very small. If n is even, then

$$\begin{aligned} 1 < \left(1 + \frac{(-1)^n}{\alpha^{2n}} \right)^q &= \exp \left(q \log \left(1 + \frac{1}{\alpha^{2n}} \right) \right) \\ &< \exp \left(\frac{q}{\alpha^{2n}} \right) < \exp \left(\frac{1}{\alpha^n} \right) \\ &< 1 + \frac{2}{\alpha^n}, \end{aligned}$$

again as $\frac{1}{\alpha^n} < \alpha^{-10^{150}}$. Hence, we obtain

$$L_n^q = \alpha^{nq} \left(1 + \frac{(-1)^n}{\alpha^{2n}} \right)^q = \alpha^{nq} (1 + \zeta_{q,n}), \quad \text{with } |\zeta_{q,n}| < \frac{2}{\alpha^n}.$$

We deduce that

$$\alpha^{nq} (1 + \zeta_{q,n}) = kF_k^p \left(1 + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \binom{k-j}{k} \left(\frac{F_{k-j}}{F_k} \right)^p \right).$$

We then have

$$\begin{aligned} |kF_k^p - \alpha^{nq}| &= \left| \alpha^{nq} \zeta_{q,n} - kF_k^p \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \binom{k-j}{k} \left(\frac{F_{k-j}}{F_k} \right)^p \right| \\ &\leq \alpha^{nq} |\zeta_{q,n}| + kF_k^p \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \binom{k-j}{k} \left(\frac{F_{k-j}}{F_k} \right)^p \\ &< \frac{2\alpha^{nq}}{\alpha^n} + \frac{6kF_k^p}{1.5^p} \end{aligned}$$

and dividing both sides of the above inequality by α^{nq} , we get

$$|kF_k^p \alpha^{-nq} - 1| < \frac{2}{\alpha^n} + \frac{kF_k^p}{\alpha^{nq}} \frac{6}{1.5^p}. \tag{2.6}$$

We check that $kF_k^p/\alpha^{nq} < 5/3$. One can see that $p > 10^{111}$. Indeed, by Lemma 1 and using the assumption that $k \leq x^{1/4}$, we have

$$p > 10^{-1}x/k > 10^{-1}x^{3/4} > 10^{-1}(10^{150})^{3/4} > 10^{111}.$$

Since then, p and n are both very large, we have

$$\frac{2}{\alpha^n} < \frac{1}{4}, \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{6}{1.5^p} < \frac{1}{4}.$$

Then, Inequality (2.6) leads to

$$\left| \frac{kF_k^p}{\alpha^{nq}} - 1 \right| < \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4} \frac{kF_k^p}{\alpha^{nq}}.$$

In particular, one can see that

$$\frac{kF_k^p}{\alpha^{nq}} < 1 + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4} \frac{kF_k^p}{\alpha^{nq}} = \frac{5}{4} + \frac{1}{4} \frac{kF_k^p}{\alpha^{nq}},$$

which implies that

$$\frac{3}{4} \frac{kF_k^p}{\alpha^{nq}} < \frac{5}{4},$$

i.e., $\frac{kF_k^p}{\alpha^{nq}} < 5/3$. Then, Inequality (2.6) implies that

$$|kF_k^p \alpha^{-nq} - 1| < \frac{2}{\alpha^n} + \frac{10}{1.5^p} < \frac{12}{1.5^{\min\{p,n\}}}, \tag{2.7}$$

as $\alpha > 1.5$.

Put

$$\Lambda_2 := kF_k^p \alpha^{-nq} - 1.$$

We check that $\Lambda_2 \neq 0$. Indeed, if $\Lambda_2 = 0$, then $\alpha^{nq} = kF_k^p \in \mathbb{Z}$, which is a contradiction since no power of α of nonzero integer exponent can be an integer. Thus, $\Lambda_2 \neq 0$. We use Matveev's theorem with

$$r := 3, \quad \alpha_1 := k, \quad \alpha_2 := F_k, \quad \alpha_3 := \alpha, \quad b_1 := 1, \quad b_2 := p, \quad b_3 := -nq.$$

Note that $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3 \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{5})$. Thus, we take $D := 2$. We know that

$$h(\alpha_1) = \log k < \log(10x), \quad h(\alpha_2) = \log F_k < 0.5k, \quad \text{and} \quad h(\alpha_3) = (\log \alpha)/2,$$

then we take

$$A_1 := 2 \log(10x), \quad A_2 := k, \quad A_3 := \log \alpha.$$

Here again, $B := 10x$. Hence, Matveev's theorem implies that

$$\log |\Lambda_2| > -1.87 \times 10^{12} k (\log(10x))^2. \tag{2.8}$$

Now, Inequalities (2.7) and (2.8) imply that

$$\min\{p, n\} < 4.7 \times 10^{12} k (\log(10x))^2. \tag{2.9}$$

Assume that $\min\{p, n\} = n$. Then, we have

$$n < 4.7 \times 10^{12} k (\log(10x))^2. \tag{2.10}$$

Inequalities (2.5) and (2.10) together with Lemma 1 imply that

$$10^{-1}x < nq < 8.5 \times 10^{25} k^3 (\log(10x))^4 < 8.5 \times 10^{25} x^{3/4} (\log(10x))^4.$$

Then, we obtain

$$x^{1/4} < 8.5 \times 10^{26} (\log(10x))^4,$$

which gives $x < 10^{149}$. This is a contradiction.

Assume that $\min\{p, n\} = p$. Then, from Inequality (2.9), we get

$$p < 4.7 \times 10^{12} k (\log(10x))^2.$$

Now, using Lemma 1, we finally obtain

$$10^{-1}x/k < p < 4.7 \times 10^{12} k (\log(10x))^2.$$

Then, one sees that

$$x < 4.7 \times 10^{13} k^2 (\log(10x))^2.$$

As $k \leq x^{1/4}$, this leads to $x^{1/2} < 4.7 \times 10^{13} (\log(10x))^2$ i.e.,

$$x^{1/4} < 7 \times 10^6 (\log(10x)).$$

We deduce that $x < 10^{36}$, which is again a contradiction. This completes the proof of Lemma 2. □

2.2. Value of t_2

The goal of this subsection is the proof of the next lemma.

Lemma 3. *If $x > 10^{1520}$, then $p > x^{1/9}$.*

Proof. As for the proof of Lemma 2, we assume that $x > 10^{1520}$ and that $p \leq x^{1/9}$ in order to get a contradiction.

Since $x > 10^{1520} > 10^{150}$, by Lemma 2, we have

$$k/2 > (1/2)x^{1/4} > 5 \times 10^{379}.$$

Using Lemma 1 together with the fact that $k/2 > (1/2)x^{1/4}$, we have

$$p < 10x/k < 10k^3 < 100(k/2)^3 < (k/2)^4.$$

Put $l = \lfloor k/2 \rfloor + 1$. One can certainly see that $l > k/2 > p^{1/4}$. Let $j \in \{l, \dots, k\}$. We have

$$\frac{p}{\alpha^{2j}} \leq \frac{(k/2)^4}{\alpha^{2l}} < \frac{(k/2)^4}{\alpha^{k+2}} < \frac{1}{\alpha^{k/2}},$$

where we used the inequality $(k/2)^4 < \alpha^{k/2+2}$, for $k \geq 50$. So from Inequality (19) in [1], we deduce that

$$s = \frac{\alpha^{(k+1)p}(k\alpha^p - (k+1))}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2} (1 + \tau_{k,p}),$$

where $|\tau_{k,p}| < 30/\alpha^{k/2}$. This means that

$$\left| \frac{\alpha^{(k+1)p}(k\alpha^p - (k+1))}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2} - s \right| < \frac{30\alpha^{(k+1)p}(k\alpha^p - (k+1))}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2\alpha^{k/2}}. \tag{2.11}$$

So our equation (1.8) leads to

$$\left| \frac{\alpha^{(k+1)p}(k\alpha^p - (k+1))}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2} - L_n^q \right| < \frac{30\alpha^{(k+1)p}(k\alpha^p - (k+1))}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2\alpha^{k/2}}.$$

Dividing both sides of the above inequality by L_n^q , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \alpha^{(k+1)p} \left(\frac{k\alpha^p - (k+1)}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2} \right) L_n^{-q} - 1 \right| &< \frac{30\alpha^{(k+1)p}(k\alpha^p - (k+1))}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2\alpha^{k/2}L_n^q} \\ &< \frac{30\alpha^{(k+1)p}(k\alpha^p - (k+1))}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2\alpha^{k/2}k\alpha^{(k-1)p}}, \end{aligned} \tag{2.12}$$

where we used the fact that $L_n^q = s > kF_k^p > k\alpha^{k-2}$. Now, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\alpha^{(k+1)p}(k\alpha^p - (k+1))}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2k\alpha^{(k-1)p}} &= \frac{\alpha^{2p}(k\alpha^p - (k+1))}{k5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2} < \frac{\alpha^{3p}}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2} \\ &< \frac{\alpha^{3p}}{\alpha^{1.6p}(\alpha^p - 1)^2} < 6, \end{aligned}$$

where we used the fact that $\sqrt{5} > \alpha^{1.6}$ as well as the fact that $\alpha^{3t} - 6\alpha^{1.6t}(\alpha^t - 1)^2 < 0$, for every real number $t \geq 1$. So, Inequality (2.12) leads to

$$\left| \alpha^{(k+1)p} \left(\frac{k\alpha^p - (k+1)}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2} \right) L_n^{-q} - 1 \right| < \frac{180}{\alpha^{k/2}}. \tag{2.13}$$

Put

$$\Lambda_3 = \alpha^{(k+1)p} \left(\frac{k\alpha^p - (k+1)}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2} \right) L_n^{-q} - 1.$$

We will prove that $\Lambda_3 \neq 0$, under the assumption $x > 10^{1520}$. Assuming that $\Lambda_3 = 0$, we get

$$k\alpha^p - (k+1) = \Delta_p^2 5^{p/2} \alpha^{-(k+1)p} L_n^q,$$

where $\Delta_p = \alpha^p - 1$. Taking the norms in $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{5})$, we get

$$|((-1)^p - L_p + 1)k^2 + (2 - L_p)k + 1| = 5^p L_n^{2q} |(-1)^p - L_p + 1|^2.$$

If p is even, we get

$$|(L_p - 2)k^2 + (L_p - 2)k - 1| = 5^p L_n^{2q} |L_p - 2|^2. \tag{2.14}$$

So $L_p - 2$ divides $(L_p - 2)k^2 + (L_p - 2)k - 1$, which implies that $L_p - 2$ divides 1, i.e., $L_p - 2 = \pm 1$. Thus, $p \in \{1, 2\}$, and only $p = 2$ is convenient and the left-hand side of (2.14) is smaller than $2k^2$ since $L_p - 2 = \pm 1$. So, we obtain

$$2k^2 > 5^p L_n^{2q} |L_p - 2|^2 = 5^p L_n^{2q} \geq 5L_n^{2q},$$

showing that $L_n^q < k$, which is false since $L_n^q = kF_k^p + (k-1)F_{k-1}^p + \dots + 2F_2^p + F_1^p > k$.

If p is odd, we get

$$|L_p k^2 + (L_p - 2)k - 1| = 5^p L_n^{2q} L_p^2 \tag{2.15}$$

and the left-hand side of (2.15) is smaller than $2k^2 L_p^2$. So, we obtain

$$2k^2 L_p^2 > |L_p k^2 + (L_p - 2)k - 1| = 5^p L_n^{2q} L_p^2 \geq 5L_n^{2q} L_p^2,$$

showing again that $L_n^q < k$, which is a contradiction.

Hence, we have $\Lambda_3 \neq 0$. Now, we can again apply Matveev's Theorem, with

$$r := 3, \alpha_1 := \alpha, \alpha_2 := \frac{k\alpha^p - (k+1)}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2}, \alpha_3 := L_n,$$

$$b_1 := (k+1)p, \quad b_2 := 1, \quad b_3 := -q, \quad D := 2.$$

One can see that

$$h(\alpha_1) = (\log \alpha)/2, \quad h(\alpha_3) = \log L_n < 0.5n.$$

Now, for $h(\alpha_2)$, it is well-known that for any algebraic numbers η and γ and any integer s , we have

$$\begin{aligned} h(\eta\gamma^{\pm 1}) &\leq h(\eta) + h(\gamma), \\ h(\eta + \gamma) &\leq h(\eta) + h(\gamma) + \log 2, \\ h(\eta^s) &\leq |s| h(\eta). \end{aligned}$$

Using these properties, we have

$$\begin{aligned} h(\alpha_2) &\leq h(k\alpha^p - (k + 1)) + 2h(\alpha^p - 1) + h(5^{p/2}) \\ &\leq h(k) + ph(\alpha) + h(k + 1) + 2h(\alpha^p) + ph(5^{1/2}) + 3 \log 2 \\ &\leq (3 \log \alpha/2)p + 2 \log k + 4 \log 2 \leq 10p(\log(10x)). \end{aligned}$$

We can then take $A_1 := \log \alpha$, $A_2 := 20p(\log(10x))$, $A_3 := n$, $B = 20x$. Hence, Matveev’s theorem implies that

$$\log |\Lambda_3| > -1.87 \times 10^{13} np (\log(10x))^2, \tag{2.16}$$

and together with (2.13), we get that

$$k < \frac{2}{\log \alpha} \left(1.87 \times 10^{13} pn (\log(10x))^2 + \log 180 \right) < 7.8 \times 10^{13} pn (\log(10x))^2. \tag{2.17}$$

Since $p \leq x^{\frac{1}{5}}$ and $k > x^{\frac{1}{4}}$, it follows that

$$n > 10^{-13} \frac{k}{7.8 \left(p (\log(10x))^2 \right)} > \frac{1.28 \times 10^{-14} x^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{9}}}{(\log(10x))^2} = \frac{1.28 \times 10^{-14} x^{\frac{5}{36}}}{(\log(10x))^2} > x^{\frac{1}{8}},$$

because $x > 10^{1520}$. That is, $x < n^8$ and then we have

$$q < \frac{10x}{n} < 10n^7 < n^8 \quad \text{since} \quad n > x^{1/8} > 10.$$

Thus, one obtains

$$L_n^q = \alpha^{nq} \left(1 + \frac{(-1)^n}{\alpha^{2n}} \right)^q = \alpha^{nq} (1 + \zeta_{q,n}), \quad \text{with} \quad |\zeta_{q,n}| < \frac{2}{\alpha^n}.$$

Now, using $s = L_n^q$ and (2.11), we get

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{\alpha^{(k+1)p}(k\alpha^p - (k + 1))}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2} - \alpha^{nq} \right| \\ &= \left| \frac{\alpha^{(k+1)p}(k\alpha^p - (k + 1))}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2} - \alpha^{nq} (1 + \zeta_{q,n}) + \alpha^{nq} \zeta_{q,n} \right| \\ &= \left| \frac{\alpha^{(k+1)p}(k\alpha^p - (k + 1))}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2} - s + \alpha^{nq} \zeta_{q,n} \right| \\ &< \frac{30\alpha^{(k+1)p}(k\alpha^p - (k + 1))}{5^{p/2}(\alpha^p - 1)^2 \alpha^{k/2}} + \alpha^{nq} \zeta_{q,n} < \frac{180}{\alpha^{k/2}} + \alpha^{nq} |\zeta_{q,n}|. \end{aligned}$$

Dividing both sides by α^{nq} and using the fact that $|\zeta_{q,n}| < \frac{2}{\alpha^n}$, we obtain

$$\left| \alpha^{p(k+1)-qn} \left(\frac{(k\alpha^p - (k + 1))}{(\alpha^p - 1)^2} \right) 5^{-\frac{p}{2}} - 1 \right| < \frac{200}{\alpha^{\min\{\frac{k}{2}, n\}}}. \tag{2.18}$$

Put

$$\Lambda_4 = \alpha^{p(k+1)-qn} \left(\frac{(k\alpha^p - (k+1))}{(\alpha^p - 1)^2} \right) 5^{-\frac{p}{2}} - 1.$$

We prove that $\Lambda_4 \neq 0$. Indeed, if $\Lambda_4 = 0$, then $k\alpha^p - (k+1) = 5^{p/2} \Delta_p^2 \alpha^{qn-(k+1)p}$, and taking the norms in $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{5})$, we get the equation

$$|((-1)^p - L_p + 1)k^2 + (2 - L_p)k + 1| = 5^p |(-1)^p - L_p + 1|^2,$$

which has no solutions with $k \geq 3$ from [3]. So, $\Lambda_4 \neq 0$. Again, we will apply again Matveev’s Theorem, with

$$\begin{aligned} r &:= 3, \quad \alpha_1 := \alpha, \quad \alpha_2 := \frac{k\alpha^p - (k+1)}{(\alpha^p - 1)^2}, \quad \alpha_3 := \sqrt{5}, \\ b_1 &:= (k+1)p - qn, \quad b_2 := 1, \quad b_3 := -p, \quad D := 2. \end{aligned}$$

We have

$$h(\alpha_1) = (\log \alpha)/2, \quad h(\alpha_2) < 10p(\log(10x)), \quad \text{and } h(\alpha_3) = (\log 5)/2,$$

and we take $A_1 := \log \alpha$, $A_2 := 20p(\log(10x))$, $A_3 := \log 5$, $B = 20x$. Hence, Matveev’s theorem implies that

$$\log |\Lambda_4| > -3.01 \times 10^{13} p (\log(10x))^2, \tag{2.19}$$

and together with (2.18), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \min \left\{ \frac{k}{2}, n \right\} &< \frac{1}{\log \alpha} \left(3.01 \times 10^{13} p (\log(10x))^2 + \log 200 \right) \\ &< 6.3 \times 10^{13} p (\log(10x))^2. \end{aligned}$$

If $\min \{k/2, n\} = k/2$, then

$$k < 1.26 \times 10^{14} p (\log(10x))^2.$$

Since $k > 10^{-1}x/p$ by Lemma 1, we get $x/p < 1.26 \times 10^{15} p (\log(10x))^2$, which implies that $p > 2.82 \times 10^{-8} x^{1/2} / (\log(10x))$.

The assumption, $p \leq x^{\frac{1}{5}}$ implies that $x^{\frac{1}{5}} > 2.82 \times 10^{-8} x^{1/2} / (\log(10x))$ i.e., $x^{7/18} / (\log(10x)) < 3.55 \times 10^8$. We deduce that $x < 10^{27}$, which is false.

If $\min \{k/2, n\} = n$, then we obtain

$$n < 6.3 \times 10^{13} p (\log(10x))^2. \tag{2.20}$$

Now, from inequalities (2.17), (2.20) and Lemma 2, we get

$$x^{\frac{1}{4}} < k < 5 \times 10^{27} p^2 (\log(10x))^4 \leq 5 \times 10^{27} x^{\frac{2}{5}} (\log(10x))^4,$$

i.e.,

$$\frac{x^{\frac{1}{36}}}{(\log(10x))^4} < 5 \times 10^{27},$$

which leads to $x < 10^{1510}$. This is another contradiction and finishes the proof of Lemma 3. □

2.3. Value of t_3

The aim of this subsection is to prove the following lemma.

Lemma 4. *If $x > 10^{2099}$, then $n > x^{1/10}$.*

Proof. Suppose that $x > 10^{2099}$. Then, by Lemma 2, we have $k > x^{1/4} > 10^{524}$, and using Lemma 1, we obtain $p < 10x/k < 10k^3 < k^4$, which implies that

$$\frac{p}{\alpha^{2k}} < \frac{k^4}{\alpha^{2k}} < \frac{1}{\alpha^k},$$

since $k^4 < \alpha^k$, for $k \geq 28$.

We now write

$$F_k^p = \frac{\alpha^{kp}}{5^{p/2}} \left(1 - \frac{(-1)^k}{\alpha^{2k}} \right)^p$$

and use the similar arguments as in Lemma 3 to obtain

$$F_k^p = \frac{\alpha^{kp}}{5^{p/2}} \left(1 - \frac{(-1)^k}{\alpha^{2k}} \right)^p = \frac{\alpha^{kp}}{5^{p/2}} (1 + \zeta_{k,p}), \quad |\zeta_{k,p}| < \frac{2}{\alpha^k}.$$

We finally go back to (2.2) and use Inequality (2.3) to get

$$\left| k\alpha^{pk}5^{-\frac{p}{2}}L_n^{-q} - 1 \right| < \frac{10}{1.5^{\min\{p,k\}}}.$$

Similarly as for Λ_2 , we easily check that $k\alpha^{pk}5^{-\frac{p}{2}}L_n^{-q} - 1 \neq 0$. We can use once again Matveev's theorem to obtain

$$\min\{p, k\} < 3.3 \times 10^{14}n(\log(10x))^2.$$

Since $x > 10^{2099}$, by Lemmas 2 and 3, $\min\{p, k\} > x^{\frac{1}{9}}$ and then we get

$$n > \frac{3.03 \times 10^{-15}x^{\frac{1}{9}}}{(\log(10x))^2} > x^{\frac{1}{10}},$$

for $x > 10^{2099}$ and the proof of Lemma 4 is complete. □

2.4. Completing the Proof of Theorem 1

We start this subsection by numerically bounding x . Precisely, we want to prove that $x \leq 10^{2099}$. Assume that $x > 10^{2099}$. Then, by Lemma 4, we have $q < 10x/n < 10n^9 < n^{10}$. So, our main Equation (1.8) becomes

$$\frac{k\alpha^{pk}}{5^{\frac{p}{2}}} (1 + \zeta_{p,k}) = L_n^q = \alpha^{nq} (1 + \zeta_{q,n}),$$

with $|\zeta_{p,k}| < \frac{6}{1.5^{\min\{p,k\}}}$ and $|\zeta_{q,n}| < \frac{2}{\alpha^n}$. As $x > 10^{2099}$, by Lemmas 2, 3 and 4, we have $\min\{n, p, k\} > x^{1/10} > 10^{209}$. So, the three variables k, p and n are large and then after rearranging similarly as in Lemmas 2 and 3, we obtain

$$\left| k\alpha^{pk-qn}5^{-p/2} - 1 \right| < \frac{10}{1.5^{\min\{n,p,k\}}}.$$

Put

$$\Lambda_5 := k\alpha^{pk-qn}5^{-p/2} - 1.$$

We will distinguish two cases.

Case 1: $\Lambda_5 \neq 0$. In this case, applying Matveev’s theorem, we obtain

$$\min\{n, p, k\} < 7.43 \times 10^{12}(\log(10x))^2.$$

Observe that by Lemmas 2, 3 and 4, $\min\{n, p, k\} > x^{\frac{1}{10}}$, so that $x^{\frac{1}{10}} < 7.43 \times 10^{12}(\log(10x))^2$, which gives $x < 10^{182}$, a contradiction to $x > 10^{2099}$.

Case 2: $\Lambda_5 = 0$. In this case, we get $\alpha^{kp-nq} = 5^{p/2}/k$. Squaring this, we get $\alpha^{2(kp-nq)} = 5^p/k^2$. The only possibility is that both sides of the above equality are 1. Thus, $kp = nq$ and $k = 5^{p/2}$. In particular, p is even and

$$p = \frac{2 \log k}{\log 5} < 2 \log k < \log(10x), \tag{2.21}$$

where we used once again Lemma 1 to get $k < 10x$. Since $x > 10^{2099}$, from Lemma 3, we have $p > x^{1/9}$. Hence, inequality (2.21) leads to

$$\frac{x^{1/9}}{\log(10x)} < 2,$$

which implies that $x < 10^{18}$. This is again a contradiction. So, $x \leq 10^{2099}$, as expected.

Finally, by Lemma 1, $\max\{k, n, p, q\} < 10x \leq 10^{2100}$, which completes the proof of Theorem 1.

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References

[1] A. Altassan, and F. Luca, On the Diophantine equation $\sum_{j=1}^k jF_j^p = F_n^q$, *J. Number Theory* **217** (2020), 256–277.

- [2] Y. Bugeaud, M. Maurice, and S. Siksek, Classical and modular approaches to exponential Diophantine equations I. Fibonacci and Lucas perfect powers, *Ann. of Math.* **163** (2006), 969–1018.
- [3] K. Gueth, F. Luca and L. Szalay, On a diophantine equation involving powers of Fibonacci numbers, *Proc. Japan Acad. ser. A Math. Sci.* **96** (4) (2020), 33–37.
- [4] K. Györy, On the Diophantine equation $\binom{n}{k} = x^l$, *Acta Arith.* **3** (1997), 289–295.
- [5] K. Liptai, Lucas balancing numbers, *Acta Math. Univ. Ostraviensis* **14** (2006), 43–47.
- [6] M. Luo, On Triangular Lucas numbers, *Applications of Fibonacci Numbers* **4** (1990), 231–240.
- [7] E. M. Matveev, An explicit lower bound for a homogeneous rational linear form in the logarithms of algebraic numbers, II, *Izv. Math.* **64**(6) (2000), 1217–1269.
- [8] G. Soydan, L. Németh, and L. Szalay, On the Diophantine equation $\sum_{j=1}^k jF_j^p = F_n^q$, *Arch. Math. (BRNO) Tomus* **54** (2008), 177–188.
- [9] E. Tchammou, and A. Togbé, On the Diophantine equation $\sum_{j=1}^k jP_j^p = P_n^q$, *Acta Math. Hungar.* **162**(2) (2020), 647–676.